

EVALUATING PROCESS EFFICIENCY, COST AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT: A HOLISTIC REVIEW OF MODERN INDUSTRIAL PRACTICES IN BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

Dr Alfred Demenongu Tyav¹, Sabastine Liambee Nor², Depuun Jacob Nartondo³ & Simon Peter⁴

^{1, 2, 3 & 4} Department of Industrial Technology, Faculty of Technology and Industrial Studies, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi
Email: dtav@bsum.edu.ng
D.O.I.: 10.5281/zenodo.20306861

Received: 16.03.2026 / Accepted: 15.04.2026 / Published: 18.05.2026

ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

This study evaluates process efficiency, cost efficiency, and environmental impact in modern industrial practices in Benue State, Nigeria. The manufacturing sector plays a vital role in economic development; however, its contribution in Nigeria has declined due to high production costs, inadequate infrastructure, low-capacity utilization, and inefficient operational strategies. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design and relied on secondary data obtained from financial reports, efficiency reports, and environmental assessment records of selected industries. From a population of 128 registered industries in Benue State, six major industries were purposively selected: Dangote Cement Company, Oracle Plastic Industry, Micap Nigeria Limited (Miva Rice), Seraph Oil, Hule Oil, and Ashi Rice Limited. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically mean and frequency. Findings revealed varying levels of efficiency among the industries. Dangote Cement Company recorded the highest process efficiency (90%) and cost efficiency (95%), while Hule Oil and Seraph Oil demonstrated the lowest process and cost efficiency levels. Environmental impact analysis showed that some industries, particularly cement and plastic production, have relatively high environmental footprints compared to others. Overall results indicate very low process efficiency (20%), low-cost efficiency (40%), and very low environmental efficiency (10%) among the studied industries. The study concludes that modern industrial practices in Benue State remain largely inefficient and recommends improvements in production processes, adoption of cost-efficient operational strategies, and implementation of environmental Process Efficiency, Cost Efficiency, Environmental Impact, Modern Industrial Practices by sustainable manufacturing practices.

KEYWORDS: Process Efficiency, Cost Efficiency, Environmental Impact, Modern Industrial Practices

INTRODUCTION

High costs of production, inadequate infrastructure, and poor capacity utilization have shrunk the contribution and performance manufacturing industries in Benue State in recent years. The situation has been exacerbated due to the resultant effect of economic recession which contributes negatively to the performance of firms. Firms and industries performance and efficiency previously in Benue State have always been analyzed using financial ratios. According Fapohunda et al, (2017), efficiency assessment of business firms is a major concern by managers and stakeholders in the light of present-day global challenges in both developed and developing countries. Efficiency assessment of a company no doubt demonstrates how shareholders and investors interests are taken into consideration. It informs them how a company's resources are used effectively and efficiently and it also motivates firms to implement strategies for further improvements (Yu, Barros, Tsai & Liao, 2014). Yu et al (2014) pointed out that data envelopment analysis (DEA) has proven to be an essential tool because it measures relative efficiencies by using multi-inputs and multi-outputs variables. Efficiency is a dynamic concept that involves a firm being able to operate with the minimum level of resources or inputs such as capital, labour, and materials to produce maximum outputs and still remain highly competitive for a considerable period of time. Assessing efficiency levels has thus become an important issue for managers of businesses in developing countries like Nigeria that is currently going through economic turbulence. Several methodologies which include scorecards, economic production function, econometric stochastic frontier analysis, multi-attribute decision making techniques and regression analysis have been employed for measuring and assessing business performance but these measures are often inadequate due to multiple inputs and outputs defined by different resources, activities and environmental factors, thus making Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) becomes a viable alternative (Osamwonyi & Imafidon, 2015).

A firm is regarded as efficient if it is able to employ moderate costs to generate higher revenue; and on the other hand, a firm is facing inefficiency in terms of technical and allocative in efficiency and that implies it is still not operating at its optimal level. The importance of the efficiency of manufacturing firms cannot be overemphasized in an economy. They contribute largely to economic activities; making goods available to consumers via appropriate medium. The manufacturing sector in Benue State has a great potential in promoting economic growth and competitiveness of the State. The most frequently cited problems of manufacturing firms in Nigeria include physical infrastructure, followed by access to credit, insufficient demand, and cost of imported raw materials and lack of skilled labour (Soderbom & Teal, 2022).

The Nigerian Stock Exchange (2010) indicates that thirty percent of industries were closed down, sixty percent of industries classified as ailing and only ten percent classified as operating at sustainable level. All these indicate that the efficiency of the Nigerian quoted manufacturing industries is in doubt. Aniemene (2017) observed that for this, leaders of manufacturing firms are adopting efficient processes to achieve continuous manufacturing improvement and higher production performance. Most manufacturing firms provide essential goods to support the quality of human life and contribute to a nations' economy. Furthermore, Obioma et al. (2015) analyzed the productivity of manufacturing firms and found that the manufacturing sector has added substantially to the GDP of many countries. Nonetheless, the contribution of the Nigerian manufacturing sector to the Nigerian GDP has continued to decline due to operational inefficiency (Olorunfemi, Obamuyi, Adekunjo, & Ogunleye, 2013). Obioma et al. further observed that many manufacturing industries in Nigeria experience challenges caused by low-capacity utilization that has resulted in

inefficient processes. Onuoha (2013) maintained that the inefficient manufacturing process had aggravated the inability of the Nigerian manufacturing sector to provide employment opportunities, reduce the nation's level of poverty, and increase profitability. To remain competitive, leaders of manufacturing firms should adopt efficient production practice that allows for rapid responses to most manufacturing problems. A transformation of Nigeria's manufacturing industry is imperative to create employment opportunities, increased productivity, revenue generation, and economic transformation (Aiyedogbon & Anyanwu, 2015).

The primary goal of a firm's existence is to make profit and then increase earnings in order for the business to remain relevant in the industry. Nonetheless, the greatest technique to increase profit is to expand the possibility of sales and create a smart cost-cutting strategy. As a result, the high cost of raw materials and general expenses has put a strain on the profitability margin of many businesses in recent years (Obafemi & Taiwo 2023). It has been observed that an efficient firm performance can be attained if the company's financial structure is built in such a way that the cost of capital is kept to a bare minimum (Dare & Sola, 2017). However, in a competitive market where consumers are constantly seeking high-quality products or services at a reasonable price and shareholders are similarly wanting a significant rate of return on their investment, it is vital for the company's management to identify a good channel to please the shareholders in terms of returns on investment as well as the consumers by giving the best items.

Cost is the expenses incurred in the course of realizing revenue or implementing a project, which can be classified as fixed, variable, or semi-variable in nature (Enyi, 2017). It is the total of all payments made to factors of production involved in the manufacture of that commodity. According to Alireza and Mahdi (2016), the performance of every organization is primarily defined by how well it manages its costs. This is due in part to the fact that in order to maximize profit, costs must be kept to a bare minimum. Cost cutting has become a critical technique for businesses to use in order to keep ahead of the rising competition in the business climate. In light of the aforementioned, this study will assess the potential effect and relationship of cost-cutting approaches in producing effective performance in modern industrial practices that will keep the industries in Benue State afloat in a competitive climate (Obafemi & Taiwo 2023). Olukade and Isichei (2021) however opined that this reality has created an increasing competition that has led to the displacements of some manufacturing concerns, as modern technological advancement has led to the outgrowing of their value and thus being replaced by value-driven, service-rendering organizations. This has created challenges for the sector and has led to some manufacturing concerns to re-evaluate their approach to their continued existence from a completely different perspective (Ahmad, 2012).

The growth of any company is largely determined by how well it can manage its costs. This is partly because to be able to maximize profit, cost must be reduced to the barest minimum (Adewara et al, 2019). Cost reduction has become a vital tool for industries to constantly stay ahead of the increased competition in the business environment. Indeed, even organizations that are gainful can profit by implementing cost-lessening techniques to make considerably higher overall revenue on its items or administrations. According to Ogunnaike (2010), the effective and efficient management of cost is not only necessary to meet the profit objective of the company but also the going concern status of the entity. To record growth in terms of increase in profit of an organization, cost reduction mechanism should be put in place. Low production costs has become one of the primary ways that organizations compete in a global economy, hence, cost reduction must continually be in the minds of managers of

organization. Cost reduction is a planned approach to reduce expenditure. It is a continuous process of examining critically all elements of cost and each aspect of the business with a view to improving business efficiency. According to Adeniyi (2001), cost reduction starts with an assumption that current cost levels or planned cost levels are too high despite the fact that cost control may be good and organization experiencing high efficiency levels. Labour costs form a significant portion of overheads of most businesses regardless of whatever industry they belong to (Tonkins, 2016). Since labour costs form a significant portion of business costs, increased labour costs increase the cost of doing business and these costs is transferred to customers in high prices. According to the law of demand which states that the higher the price the lower the demand and vice versa, sales will reduce because of the increase in price (Egbide, Otekunrin, Bamidele, Adewara & Olufemi, 2019). Therefore, it can be said that labour costs affect business turnover (sales). Since manufacturing industries need increased sales to experience growth, hence, it can be conclusively said that labour costs affect the growth of industries.

Environmental sustainability has become a critical concern globally, with industries playing a significant role in contributing to environmental degradation. In Nigeria, the manufacturing sector is a vital part of the economy, yet it faces challenges in implementing sustainable practices (Fwadwabea, et al 2024). Manufacturing industries are pivotal to the economic development of Nigeria. However, their operations often lead to significant environmental degradation, including air and water pollution, deforestation, and greenhouse gas emissions (Akintoye et al., 2019). The concept of environmental sustainability necessitates that industries operate in ways that do not deplete natural resources or cause long-term ecological damage. Nigerian manufacturing industries face numerous environmental challenges, including air and water pollution, resource depletion, and waste management issues. According to Akintoye et al. (2019), these industries significantly contribute to environmental degradation, which is exacerbated by inadequate regulatory frameworks and enforcement mechanisms. The cement, textile, and food processing industries are particularly notorious for their environmental impacts.

Statement of the Problem

Approximately 30% of the manufacturing plants in Nigeria have closed, and almost 60% are not meeting operational goals, leaving only 10% operating at a sustainable level leading to decreased productivity and profitability (Agu, Anichebe, & Maduagwu, 2016). It has been observed also that over 50% of manufacturing firms in Nigeria (Benue State inclusive) experienced a decline in production capacity utilization and profitability because of the inefficient manufacturing process (Okafor, 2013). The general business problem is that most manufacturing industries in Nigeria experienced operational inefficiency due to inadequate business strategy limiting organizations profitability. The specific business problem is that some leaders of manufacturing firms in Benue State lacked effective process and cost management strategies to support efficient manufacturing operations. According to Aniemene (2017), over the past few years, Nigeria's inflation rate has been growing steadily. The inflation rate reached its greatest level since 1996, which was 33.7%, as of April 2024. Compared to the previous month, January 2024, this represents an increase from 29.9% to 31.7%.

Despite the significant contribution made by manufacturing sector in the past to the growth of Nigeria economy, the high costs of production, inadequate infrastructure, and poor capacity utilization have shrunk the contribution and performance in recent years. The situation has been exacerbated due to the resultant effect of economic recession in 2015 which contributes

negatively to the performance of firms in Nigeria. Consequently, many manufacturing industries had been crippled and struggling to survive which oftentimes led to loss of jobs and leaves some industries in the brick of collapse which ultimately led to a decrease in productivity and profitability. Owing to the above challenges, some industries experienced an unprecedented closure of factories and low production.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to evaluate process efficiency, cost and environmental impact in modern industrial practices. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Evaluate industrial process efficiency in major industries in Benue State.
2. Evaluate industrial cost efficiency in major industries in Benue State.
3. Assess environmental efficiency in major industries in Benue State.
4. Assess the overall industrial efficiency of the major industries in Benue State

Research Questions

1. How efficient is industrial processes in major industries in Benue State?
2. How efficient is industrial operational cost in major industries in Benue State?
3. How efficient is the industries operation on the environment in major industries in Benue State?
4. What is the overall industrial efficiency of the major industries in Benue State

Methodology

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design. The research design was adopted since it relied on existing data to allow a complete assessment of the process efficiency, cost efficiency and environmental impact of listed industries in Benue State. The population for the study is 128 registered industries in Benue State. A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select six major industries in Benue State. These industries include Dangote Cement Company, Tse-Kucha, Gboko Local Government, Oracle Plastic Industry Makurdi Local Government, Micap Nigeria Limited (Miva Rice) Makurdi Local Government, Seraph Oil Makurdi Local Government, Hule Oil Annune, Tarka Local Government and Ashi Rice Limited Anyiin, Logo Local Government. The reason for selecting these industries is that they are major industries in Benue State; therefore, they will have records of data on process efficiency, cost efficiency and environmental impact. Secondary data was the main source of data for the study. The data was obtained from financial reports, raw material efficiency report, labour efficiency, overhead efficiency, performance report and environmental assessment report of the selected manufacturing industries in Benue state. The statistical tools that were used for data analysis in this research were mean and frequency.

Research Question 1: How efficient is industrial process in major industries in Benue State?

Table 1: Frequency Showing Industrial Process Efficiency of the Six Major Industries in Benue State.

Data presented in Table 1 shows the level of process efficiency of industries in Benue State. The analysis shows that Dangote Cement Company has the highest level of process efficiency (90%), followed by Oracle Plastic Industry (80), then Micap Nigeria Limited (60). The analysis further shows that; Hule Oil, Anune has the lowest of process efficiency (40%), followed by Seragh Oil Makurdi (50%) and Ashi Rice Limited Anyiin (50%).

Research Question 2: How efficient is industrial operational cost in major industries in Benue State?

Table 2: Frequency Showing Industrial Cost Efficiency of the Six Major Industries in Benue State.

Data presented in Table 2 shows the level of cost efficiency of industries in Benue State. The analysis shows that Dangote Cement Company has the highest level of cost efficiency (95%), followed by Ashi Rice Limited (80%) then Oracle Plastic Industry (70%) and Micap Nigeria Limited (70%). The result further shows that; Seragh Oil Makurdi has the lowest of cost efficiency (50%), followed by Hule Oil Anune (60).

Research Question 3: How efficient is the industries operation on the environment in major industries in Benue State?

Table 3: Frequency Showing Environmental Impact of the Six Major Industries in Benue State

Data presented in Table 3 shows the level of environmental impact of industries in Benue State. The analysis shows that Dangote Cement Company has very high impact on environmental (89%), followed by Oracle Plastic Industry (60%), then Micap Nigeria Limited (50%). The result further shows that Ashi Rice Limited has a lower impact on environment (25%) followed by Seragh Oil Makurdi (40%), then Hule Oil Anune (45%).

Research Question 4: What is the overall industrial efficiency of the major industries in Benue State?

Table 4: Frequency Showing Overall Industrial Efficiency of the Major Industries in Benue State.

Data presented in Table 4 shows the overall industrial efficiency of the major industries in Benue State. From the data it was seen that industries in Benue State attain a very low process efficiency (20%), low-cost efficiency (40%) and very low environmental efficiency (10%). This implies that modern manufacturing processes in Benue State are inefficient.

Discussion of Findings

Results on process efficiency of industries in Benue State revealed that industries in Benue State attain very low process efficiency (20%). In line with the finding, Fapohunda et al, (2017) noted that efficiency assessment of business firms is a major concern by managers and stakeholders in the light of present-day global challenges in both developed and developing countries.

Results on cost efficiency of industries in Benue State revealed that industries in Benue State attain low-cost efficiency (40%). Supporting this, Egbide, et al (2019) points out that the growth of any company is largely determined by how well it can manage its costs. This is partly because to be able to maximize profit, cost must be reduced to the barest minimum. Cost reduction has become a vital tool for industries to constantly stay ahead of the increased competition in the business environment (Alireza & Mahdi, 2012). Indeed, even organizations that are gainful can profit by implementing cost-lessening techniques to make considerably higher overall revenue on its items or administrations. According to Ogunnaike (2010), the effective and efficient management of cost is not only necessary to meet the profit objective of the company but also the going concern status of the entity. To record growth in terms of increase in profit of an organization, cost reduction mechanism should be put in place.

Results on environmental impacts of industries in Benue State revealed that industries in Benue State have a negative impact on environment as seen their low-cost efficiency level of 40%. Along the same line, Fwadwabea et al (2024) stated that environmental sustainability has become a critical concern globally, with industries playing a significant role in

contributing to environmental degradation. In Nigeria, the manufacturing sector is a vital part of the economy, yet it faces challenges in implementing sustainable practices.

Result on overall industrial efficiency of the major industries in Benue State revealed that industries in Benue State attain a very low process efficiency (20%), low-cost efficiency (40%) and very low environmental efficiency (10%). Efficiency assessment of a company no doubt demonstrates how shareholders and investors interests are taken into consideration. It informs them how a company's resources are used effectively and efficiently and it also motivates firms to implement strategies for further improvements (Yu, Barros, Tsai & Liao, 2014).

Conclusion

Many manufacturing industries in Nigeria experience challenges caused by low-capacity utilization that has resulted in inefficient processes. It has revealed from the study that industries in Benue State attain very low process efficiency (20%), low-cost efficiency (40%) and very low environmental efficiency (10%). These results imply that modern manufacturing processes in Benue State are inefficient. Thus, there is a need to constantly evaluate industries efficiency in Benue State. If this is not checked, industries in Benue State will continue to be inefficient.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that industries in Benue State should improve on their production processes. It was also recommended that industries in Benue State should adopt cost efficient production practices. This will help minimize cost of production and hence maximize profit. Finally, it was recommended that industries in Benue State should adopt environmentally friendly production processes. This will reduce the impact of industries operation on environment.

References

- Adeniyi, S. O. (2017). The impact of human resource accounting on the profitability of a firm: empirical evidence from access bank of Nigeria Plc. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing, and Finance Research*, 3(7), 76-94
- Agu, O. A., Anichebe, N. A., & Maduagwu, N. E. (2016). Impact of globalisation on Nigeria manufacturing sector: A study of selected manufacturing firms in Enugu. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 5(5), 44-54.
- Akintoye, A. S., Adediran, M. A., & Ogundipe, O. A. (2019). Environmental impacts of manufacturing activities in Nigeria. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26(29), 30314- 30324.
- Alireza, A. S., & Mahdi, A. (2012). Target and Kaizen costing. *International Journal of Social, Behavioural, Educational, Economic, Business and Industrial engineering*, 6(2), 171.

- Ahmad, S. (2012). Impact of organizational culture on performance management practices in Pakistan. *Business International Journal*, 5(1), 50–55
- Aniemene, F. (2017). *Strategies for increased productivity through control of process constraints*. (Doctoral thesis), Walden University
- Aiyedogbon, J. O., & Anyanwu, S. O. (2015). Microeconomic determinants of industrial development in Nigeria. *Nile Journal of Business and Economics*, 1(1), 37-46.
- Egbide, B., Otekunrin, E.R. Bamidele, R. Adewara, S., & Olufemi, O. (2019). Cost reduction strategies and the growth of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology* 10(3), 305–312.
- Fwadwabea, T., Amos, K.G. & Ope-Ojo, O.E. (2024). Environmental sustainability in Nigerian manufacturing industries: A life cycle assessment of production processes. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)*, 11(7), 1065-1073.
- Ogunnaike, M. W. (2010). Cost management and profitability in manufacturing companies (Undergraduate Thesis). Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria.
- Olukade, F.T., & Isichei, E.E. (2021). Process improvement and performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.” *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 23(5), 2021, 1-13.
- Onuoha, B.C. (2013). An analysis of the operational environments of manufacturing firms in Aba, South-East, Nigeria. *International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7(1), 180-208.
- Yu, H., Abdullah, A., & Mohd Saat, R. (2014). Overcoming time and ethical constraints in the qualitative data collection process: A case of information literacy research. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 46, 243-257.